

Evolution of the mineral concentration and bioaccumulation of the black soldier fly, *Hermetia illucens*, feeding on two different larval media

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Table S1. Percentage recoveries of each element in the randomly spiked samples.¹

	Sample / replicate	Recoveries (%)									
		Ca	Cr	Cu	Fe	K	Mg	Mn	Na	Ni	Zn
Bagasse	Final diet / b3	99	101	104	101	83	74	106	95	102	102
	Final diet / c2	79	101	104	100	81	56	108	91	105	101
	Larvae / a1	-	102	103	104	-	65	105	84	104	100
	Larvae / c3	42	108	111	110	97	105	113	107	109	110
	Pupae / a2	-	96	96	99	54	79	99	85	97	95
	Adults / a2	174	153	157	157	119	146	158	140	155	153
Hen feed	Adults / c3	140	111	113	114	65	93	117	100	114	107
	Larvae / a1	-	112	114	112	58	104	115	105	114	112
	Pupae / c2	-	107	110	106	-	37	98	95	107	105

¹ Is marked with – when there are no recoveries for those elements.

Table S2. Percentage recoveries using scandium (Sc) and yttrium (Y) as internal standards of each element in the randomly spiked samples.¹

	Sample / replicate	Recoveries (%)							
		Sc				Y			
		Ca	K	Mg	Na	Ca	K	Mg	Na
Bagasse	Final diet / b3	51	44	33	52	43	37	28	44
	Final diet / c2	73	77	55	85	70	73	51	82
	Larvae / a1	264	267	182	128	-	-	50	75
	Larvae / c3	-	14	34	49	-	13	29	42
	Pupae / a2	-	38	58	71	-	-	-	-
	Adults / a2	150	185	163	130	80	61	70	66
Hen feed	Adults / c3	184	139	146	143	138	225	167	124
	Larvae / a1	171	147	156	138	198	143	136	113
	Pupae / c2	-	-	33	123	62	-	63	119

¹ Is marked with – when there are no recoveries for those elements.